

Selecting a Nesstar Replacement for Odesi

Odesi Nesstar Replacement Working Group¹

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Executive Summary

This document has been adapted from a report presented to the [Ontario Council of University Libraries](#) (OCUL) by the Odesi Nesstar Replacement Working Group. This was a working group of [OCUL Data Community](#) (ODC) members who gathered between June 2021 and February 2022 to explore options for replacing the Odesi Nesstar repository tool.

The document provides a descriptive summary of the steps undertaken by the group to make a software replacement recommendation to OCUL and its stakeholders. The steps include an environmental scan of software platforms that could be used as replacements for Nesstar and a consultation process with service providers, current and previous Nesstar users at other institutions, and OCUL members. Among the group's outputs was a preliminary list of functional requirements for migration to the new platform, which is included in this summary. As a result, Scholars Portal is moving forward with the migration of Odesi to Borealis, the Canadian Dataverse Repository. The Background section offers some context for the Working Group's approach and decision-making process.

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Background

Established in 2008, the Canadian Odesi repository (<https://www.odesi.ca>) provides access to 6,000+ social science datasets, including microdata and census data from Statistics Canada, Canadian public opinion data, and other sources. Developed and maintained by Scholars Portal, it is an ongoing service of the [Ontario Council of University Libraries](#) (OCUL). In the past few years, access to Odesi has also been expanded to include universities outside of Ontario, elsewhere in Canada.

After over 10 years providing data access and tools to the Canadian research community, the repository infrastructure is due for an upgrade. Starting in 2022, the platform's back-end began migrating from Nesstar to Dataverse, a state-of-the-art, open-source, DDI-compliant repository platform. The current project phase involves migrating all data collections into a test instance of [Borealis, the Canadian Dataverse Repository](#), also maintained at Scholars Portal.

Odesi also functions as a data discovery service and data exploration tool, popular across OCUL's diverse members and outside of Ontario, the Odesi search site provides users with a catalogue to access its collections. Odesi users rely on the catalogue and repository to search and find relevant datasets, preview data and variables, and explore and analyse data in the site, before downloading files for further analysis. Odesi also helps new and experienced users explore datasets by topics, using controlled vocabularies, such as labour, economy, demography, health, and more. Datasets are packaged with all required documentation and are often ready to use in the user's software of choice without additional coding. For this reason, a concurrent, front-end redevelopment was planned that would provide continued support for typical use cases, as well as improving the platform's existing features, and enhancing the discoverability and access to these valuable research data resources.

Odesi remains an important service to provide access to OCUL collections, and support the mandate of advancing research, teaching, and the learning missions of OCUL schools. Odesi provides a cost-effective and collaborative storage, discovery, and access service for microdata and other statistical data products—resources that can be standardized across institutions and do not lend themselves well to traditional repository platforms.

The [Data Documentation Initiative](#) (DDI) metadata standard was embraced years ago by the OCUL Data Community, and by Odesi, due to its granularity, flexibility, and interoperability with other schemas and technologies, and for many years ODC members have played a role

in the support and continued development of DDI. The commitment to and use of the DDI standard demonstrates a level of support for best practices on par with other major social science data archives around the world (ICPSR, UKDA, CESSDA, etc.).

Datasets in Odesi collections are marked up and curated directly by OCUL library staff and students through the successful, distributed, OCUL MarkIt! Student Metadata Program. The MarkIt! Program is coordinated by Scholars Portal and MarkIt! Program Committee, which is also responsible for the selection, deposit, and maintenance of the Odesi data collections.

The Current Odesi Infrastructure

The current Nesstar software makes up two out of three components of the Odesi service: the Nesstar Repository in the back-end, and Nesstar Publisher, a stand-alone metadata editor and administrative server management tool. The third component is the Odesi search catalogue, which is a custom search interface developed by Scholars Portal. The front-end is coupled with the Scholars Portal MarkLogic metadata database, which harvests metadata from Nesstar, and indexes study and variable-level DDI metadata for searching.

Developed originally by the Norwegian Social Science Data Archive (NSD) and provided by NSD as a licensed software (at a cost of ~\$15k per year), Nesstar supports OCUL publishers with creating, editing, and publishing data and metadata to the web. At the time of its release, and for over a decade, Nesstar was considered quite transformative for online data exploration and analysis, with support for variable and question level descriptions, cross tabulations, subsetting, filtering, and statistical analysis. Through its component programs and server structure, Nesstar enabled robust server and file management, as well as local curation, and central repository access for distribution of Odesi's data.

The last official Nesstar software upgrade was released in 2015. In 2020, NSD designated Nesstar an end-of-life software platform. Nesstar's underlying operating system will meet end-of-life around 2023 and no new versions of the software are planned.

Environmental Scan

In 2021, the Odesi Nesstar Replacement Working Group was tasked with conducting an environmental scan of software platforms that could be used as replacements for Nesstar. In the absence of any obvious replacement products, Odesi identified a set of peer data archives that were also using or previously used Nesstar, and who were similarly looking for solutions. These included the Australian Data Archive (ADA), Abacus (provided by the University of British Columbia UBC), and the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA), which was at the time, migrating and/or developing Dataverse for this purpose. The Nesstar Replacement Working Group took care to also consider any viable commercial solutions as alternatives, also weighing the cost and degree of customization or further development that would be required to meet OCUL's needs.

Through this review, the group sought to understand the gap that must be filled when Nesstar is decommissioned, while also getting a sense of any new features found in the

software options that are currently available. The group's evaluation looked at how well these platforms might support the functions or features that Odesi required.

Please note that the Working Group's review and evaluation was conducted in the period of mid-2021, according to how each platform would fit the particular needs of the Odesi community, as defined in the group's [Functional Requirements](#). Also, in line with Scholars Portal's sustained francization³ efforts, an additional requirement the Working Group considered in its review and evaluation was a platform's ability to support a fully bilingual (French and English) service.

During the course of this investigation, the Working Group reviewed and evaluated four possible software solutions: [Colectica](#), [MTNA Rich Data Services](#), [NADA Data Catalog](#) and [Dataverse \(Borealis, the Canadian Dataverse Repository\)](#). These software platforms were selected for review because they were either already being used by data repositories similar to Odesi, or because they had already been chosen as replacements for Nesstar by other institutions.

To gain a better understanding of the platforms being evaluated, the Working Group consulted with the platform providers Colectica and MTNA, as well as a number of data repositories who had already selected platforms to migrate from Nesstar (listed in Table 1). All repositories approached had in common that they required comprehensive support for the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) metadata standard.

The Working Group conducted interviews with the platform providers and repositories mentioned above. The interviews took the form of open-ended meetings based on a common set of questions for service providers and platform developers. The questions are listed in Table 2, below.

Table 1: Data Repositories Consulted

Repository name	Software platform used
Closer	Colectica
International Household Survey Network	NADA
Abacus Data Network (UBC)	Dataverse
Australian Data Archive	Dataverse
CESSDA	Dataverse

³ Barrett, K., Handren, K., & Pagotto, S. (2020, April 6). [La francisation de Scholars Portal: Progrès vers le bilinguisme, deuxième partie](#). *OPEN SHELF*.

Repository Services	Platforms (Vendors)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What was your experience switching from Nesstar? • What platform did you switch to? • How is this going? User experience? Changes to workflows, etc.? • What are your levels of curation? Has this changed? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What Nesstar-like features does it provide? • What else is needed to set up this solution? • Other features (e.g. DDI flavour, APIs, etc.)? • Open conversation about migration options, formats, setup, etc.

Findings

The outputs of the environmental scan—interview notes, questionnaire responses and software review—were compiled into various formats for internal sharing and discussion by OCUL and the data community. Below, we share a brief summary of the benefits and limitations for each potential replacement solution. ***Please note that our review was based on the technical features that were available at that time for each of the platforms reviewed, and may not reflect the platforms’ current functionality.**

Colectica

Colectica’s Lifecycle metadata tool provides linkages between datasets and concepts over time. This would be a new area for us to consider. It also provides a fulsome DDI Editor for creating metadata. There has been some discussion about the possibility of Statistics Canada using this as a platform, which would create some potential for downstream reuse of metadata for Odesi.

However, because Colectica is a licensed product, there would be licensing costs, in addition to custom developments to meet the set of base level requirements outlined at the start of the evaluation. The group did not receive licensing cost estimates, but it is expected that they would be high based on our needs given that multiple Colectica products would need to be licensed to replace the Nesstar repository and editor components. Further, the lack of French support would make it difficult to move ahead with this product.

MTNA RDS

The MTNA RDS interface is a really sleek tool and reminiscent of some vendor data platforms like Tableau. The focus on data visualisation and data analysis, as well as access to data via APIs, is of interest. Unfortunately, since we require a metadata editor and functionality to manage DDI metadata, in addition to the repository system, and a front-end data catalogue, this system only provides a fraction of what we need to replace Nesstar. It is also a licensed product, so there are unknown licensing costs. Similarly to Colectica, the lack of French support would make it difficult to move ahead with this product.

NADA

This is the most Nesstar-like option we reviewed. It provides an editor and repository/catalogue system, and is currently being used by countries and statistical offices affiliated with the World Bank's International Household Survey Program, so there is strong community support. Unfortunately the metadata editor piece is not yet available or open, so we could not test this. It is expected to be released soon, but NADA is unsure if they will be able to licence it. If the editor was made available, this would only replace the Nesstar Publisher; NADA Repository would be an additional component infrastructure required, and it does not do everything the Nesstar Repository does, including tabulation and analysis, so there would be some loss of functionality for our end-users.

Dataverse

Dataverse appears to be the current preferred option as a replacement for Nesstar. A significant portion of previous Nesstar users (repositories) have chosen to migrate to this platform and report being pleased with their decision.

Dataverse offers an open-source, fully internationalized, robust, scalable data repository solution, with a connected Data Curation Tool (variable level DDI editor) and Data Explorer (preview and tabulation). Importantly, this option would allow OCUL to leverage an existing SP platform. Further, as the use of Dataverse is national in scope, there is potential for Odesi's data to reach a larger target audience, and to expand the shared workflows for curation and data markup.

However, Dataverse is designed for sharing research data and, accordingly, requires some custom development to make it suitable for social science survey data. Moving forward, there is growing interest in potential collaborations among repositories that previously used Nesstar to allow Dataverse to better support these data, but no current initiatives exist.

Recommendation: Dataverse software

After evaluating the different potential replacements for Nesstar, Dataverse was selected as the best repository option for supporting Odesi's metadata and data files.

The main reasons for this decision were Dataverse's built-in support for the DDI Metadata Standard, its tabular survey data ingest features, and the functionality provided by the open-source [Data Curation Tool](#) and [Dataverse Data Explorer](#), both of which were developed at Scholars Portal to integrate with Borealis.

One of Dataverse's key advantages is its robust bilingual support. This will allow Odesi to deliver data and services through a fully bilingual (French and English) interface, including a bilingual search and browse functionality, as well as supporting bilingual metadata. It should be noted also that Scholars Portal already hosts [Borealis](#), an instance of the Dataverse software to which the Odesi repository will be migrated.

For more details on which Dataverse (Borealis) features were considered decisive in making a recommendation, please see the [Functional Requirements](#) section below.

Functional Requirements

In order to help understand the scope of work needed to support Odesi data within Dataverse, the Working Group identified a preliminary list of functional requirements. This list is based on existing features, metrics and other functionality provided by Nesstar in Odesi, as well as feedback from consultations with providers and users of potential software replacement solutions, other repositories, and the OCUL Data Community, obtained at two periods throughout 2021-2022.

Table 4 lays out the requirements, as well as an assessment of how well the latest Dataverse release can support each feature.

Priority	Requirement	Nesstar	Dataverse
High	Allow setting permissions at the file level	Yes	Available
High	Support DDI metadata and Codebook (v. 2.1. minimum)	Yes	Available
High	Support open metadata for both open and restricted data	Yes	Available
High	Sharing metadata via harvesting (OAI, APIs)	No ^a	Available
High	Indexing in search engines (Google)	No	Available
High	File-level persistent linking	No	Available
High	Licensing and Terms of Use (may be helpful if odesi.ca does begin curating research data)	Yes	Available
High	Support assigning categories, subjects, and keywords	Yes	Available ^b
High	Current search site can be integrated into replacement & provide similar functionality	Yes	Available ^b
High	Exporting data in different formats (SPSS, STATA, SAS, Excel) , or some workflow to support various formats at ingest	Yes	Available ^b
High	Accessibility (full AODA compliance)	No	Available ^b
High	Easy back-end reporting for admins	No	Available ^b

Table 4: Functional Requirements

Priority	Requirement	Nesstar	Dataverse
Medium	Viewing summary statistics including descriptive frequencies at the variable level	Yes	Available
Medium	Allow for data analysis (cross tabulations, regression analysis)	Yes	Available ^b
Medium	Allow for entering metadata in French	Yes	Available ^b
Medium	Support IP authentication & single sign on (e.g., Shibboleth, EZProxy login)	Yes ^d	Available ^b
Medium	Open source (or partially open source)	No	Available
Medium	APIs for import and for export/analysis	No	Available
Medium	Version control of the dataset	No	Available
Medium	Cloud-based functionality for curation by distributed teams	No	Available
Medium	Preservation functionality aligns with SP's current tech and workflows	No	Available
Medium	Easy facilitation with a locally developed knowledge base, community engagement	No	Available ^b
Medium	Improved discovery within the system for new-to-intermediate users	No	Available ^c
Low	Data is housed on local or on library storage	Yes	Available
Low	Support recoding of variables	No ^a	Not available ^c
Low	User Accounts (e.g., fave/bookmarked surveys, saved data analysis)	No	Not available ^c

Notes

^a *Unstable and not implemented.*

^b *Available but needs work.*

^c *Available in Dataverse at the moment, through external tools (Scholars Portal's [Data Curation Tool](#) and [Dataverse Data Explorer](#))*

^d *Ezproxy and IP ranges are supported in Nesstar.*

Project Status Update: 2023

As of April 2023, the Odesi Migration & Redevelopment Working Group⁴ has been working together for over a year now to carry out the recommendations put forth in this report to replace Nesstar. The new group, composed of Scholars Portal staff and stakeholders at OCUL and partner institutions, meets bi-weekly to discuss aspects of the migration and redevelopment.

During the current phase, the migration project team has worked to ensure all data and metadata from Odesi is fully migrated to Borealis while tackling many compatibility gaps between the systems. Working closely with the Odesi Markt! Program, the team has addressed metadata quality and implemented new controlled vocabularies. Alongside the addition of DataCite DOIs for Odesi datasets, these improvements will significantly enhance the discoverability of Odesi collections.

Further, with funding assistance provided by [Compute Ontario](#), an upgraded search interface provides new and enhanced searching and browsing features, in full integration with the new Borealis back-end. This will enable front-end improvements such as support for downloading files directly from the search results page, and exploring survey questions and variables using the Borealis Data Explorer.

The Odesi migration team has been creating new and updated guides, documentation, and training materials for Odesi's users, to support the transition to the new system. These materials will include an updated Odesi Best Practices Guide, Odesi User Guide, new documentation for the connected Borealis Data Explorer and Data Curation Tool, Odesi Search API, among other resources, handouts, training sessions, and videos.

An Odesi front-end and beta-release for public testing is expected before Summer 2023, followed by an open webinar to showcase the beta release and new features.⁵ Finally, the new OCUL Odesi Futures Working Group will meet regularly over 2023 to examine Odesi's overall service and sustainability model, to identify potential new stakeholders who may contribute to evolution and sustainability of the service, and to recommend potential future business models for Odesi.

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⁵ More information on the 2023 Odesi beta release can be found [on the OCUL news site](#).

Appendix A: New Odesi Architecture

Figure 1: New Odesi service architecture.